

CAN WE MAKE THE WORLD A BETTER PLACE WITH SOLAR 3D PRINTING?

In the current edition of the Journal we interviewed Mr. Markus Kayser, a Ph.D student at the MIT. Mr. Kayser was interviewed about his Solar Sinter project, a machine that can melt sand using nothing more than sun light.

We asked him about the possibility of melting diferente materials other than sand, like basalt, since basalt and sand have high melting point. The basalt rock melts from 984 °C (1803,2 F) to 1260 °C (2300 F) [1] and sand from 1600 °C (2912 F) to 1723 °C (3133,4 F) [2,3]. As Mr. Kayser developed what appears to be a simple and affordable machine, which not only melts sand but also utilizes the process of digital additive fabrication to form useful objects.

Dear reader, imagine how would life be if we could print structures to transport water from the sea into the desert? Or make changes on this machine and convert it into a chemical reactor? Would it be possible to convert a poor desert region into a gold mine of food and energy production? Which country would have the engineering capacity to promote such dramatic changes first?

Well... Sooner or latter time will tell but if you want to know more about the future, we invite you to listen to the interview and watch the machine at work into Mr. Kayser video.

[Video file \(click to open\)](#)

[Audio file \(click to open\)](#)

The multimedia files requires Adobe PDF reader to run properly.

The complete transcription of the interview will be available in the Edition of January 2017.

List of questions:

1. Mr. Kayser, where are you from? How old are you? What is your occupation?
2. What was your inspiration when you started the solar sinter project?
3. Which goals did you expect to achieve?
4. When you were in the desert melting sand. Did you use any material that helps to lower the temperature necessary to melt the sand, like sodium carbonate or calcium oxide?
5. So it may be a good assumption that the machine has achieved temperatures higher than at least 1500 °C (2732 F), do you agree with this?

1. a) During the melting process did you take any temperature measurement? If you did, what was the temperature?

6. As the sun shines everywhere would it be possible to use the solar sinter in different places and to melt different materials? Could it be used to make big structures at relatively low cost and would these structures last for a long time? With further development of the process how many new jobs do you think could be created?

7. For some time, I have studied the basalt rock. It has many different uses depending on the size and shape of the rock. But the basalt powder could have a better use. When I saw your Solar Sinter I knew that I had found that better use. Now it seems to be possible to "print" basalt structures at very low cost.

a) Have you considered using other raw materials instead of sand? Like basalt for instance?

b) Basalt is a very abrasive resistant material, so it would be possible to print basalt pipes to conduct water to places that have no water, like a desert for instance. As those pipes will last for a long time it would be possible grow crops in a former desert for generations to come? Do you like the idea of seeing thousands of copies of your machine working together to "print" a better world?

Fonte: <<http://blog.modernmechanix.com/sun-melted-sand-for-auto-roads/>>

Altimetry map

Fonte: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/1/18/Brazil_topo.jpg

c) For instance, if we look to an altimetry map of the northeast part of Brazil, it looks possible to bring salt water from the sea hundreds of kilometers into the main land, creating artificial lakes and new economical activities bringing new job opportunities? Could printing an aqueduct create these opportunities? Or even bringing water from the Amazon River to this new lake?

d) When we see those ancient aqueducts, do you imagine that these new printed structures could last as long?

Now since we are discussing new ideas, let us suppose that after a country built this water system to transport seawater to a desert region. It creates new economical opportunities, for instance turn a small fraction of the Gobi desert into a 'green production zone', where it would be possible to grow crops, do fish-farming, create nautical practices, tourism, and more.

It also would be possible to install a salt industry, since we have sun, salt water and space to allow the evaporation of the water. Then as the salt would be available as a by product of desalination, it would be possible to make a small chemical industry to produce sodium metal and chlorine gas by an altered version of the Downs process. As can be seen in the picture (below).

Change the Spring-box by a modified version of a Downs Cell. An additional power supply would be needed complete the electrical requirements, however less electricity would be required because the NaCl would be melted by the sun heat.

On the web alternative versions of the Downs cell can be found, such as this one:
http://pfrc.students.mtu.edu/wiki/Downs_Cell.

On the Downs cell the anode and cathode reactions are described by the reactions below:

8. Do you see this “hack” on the machine as a possibility to increase its capacities?

Now, as the transportation of sodium (Na) and chlorine (Cl) to a consumption area is not challenging as well as exciting enough, these two elements could be used in the same site to promote some chemical reactions to make hydrogen gas and latter electricity. As follows:

9. Do you see this set of reactions as a cycle? As the diagram 1 bellow:

I was able to find an old design of an internal combustion engine using hydrogen as fuel, which was patented by Rudolf Arnold Erren in 1935.

It appears that it would be possible to use the reaction of equation 5, to produce the required hydrogen in a separated compartment as seen in Erren's patent (US 20140216366 A1), by making the necessary changes to his design.

10. How do you see the possibility of making some changes on the solar sinter to convert it into a Downs cell? To produce Na and energy?

11. Once upon a time Germany was famous for its chemical and mechanical industry. Do you see this type of fuel as a possibility to countries like Germany, France and the US to reduce their dependency on fossil fuels?

12. If we could observe a time line, do you think that the MIT and the American industry could beat in a race the Chinese Academy of Sciences and the Chinese industry in the development, production and commercialization of hydrogen engines? Why?

13. As an Arduino user, do you think that an Arduino could be used as the microcontroler on the patente US 20140216366 A1?

Additional references

- 1- http://www.minsocam.org/msa/collectors_corner/arc/tempmagmas.htm
- 2- <https://van.physics.illinois.edu/qa/listing.php?id=1634>
- 3- <https://www.reference.com/science/melting-point-sand-8ae98160f140cea7>
- 4- <http://www.google.com/patents/US2183674>
- 5- <http://www.google.tl/patents/US1501756>
- 6- <http://blog.modernmechanix.com/sun-melted-sand-for-auto-roads/>

*Inventor,
Rudolf Arnold Erren,
By Frank S. Appelman,
attorney*

Erren Rudolf Arnold in 1935.

FIG. 2
US 20140216366 A1